

Si-Co AND Si-Zr ALLOYS/C-MATERIAL INTERFACES: WETTING VERSUS INFILTRATION

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1. Introduction

In the manufacture of competitive composite materials through reactive infiltration, a great controversy related on the controlling stage of the infiltration process still exists. This controversy is based on the real driven force controlling the infiltration, is it a governed by Darcy's law or by the chemical reaction? To clarify this open issue, a key contribution could be coming from know-how on wetting characteristics, reactivity, surface properties and thermodynamics concerning the reacting phases. The works carried out jointly between N. Eustathopoulos and J. Narciso on different infiltrating systems, i.e. Ni-Si and Al-Si, in C-porous based materials, confirmed that reactivity at the interfaces, is the real governing phenomenon [1].

To further support this conclusion, systematic investigations of wetting characteristics, reactivity, surface properties and thermodynamics concerning Si-Me/C-based substrate couples (Me = Co, Zr) have been carried out and the more relevant results obtained are reported and in this short paper.

The outcomes here presented are doubly profitable: to study reactive infiltration process per se and to make progress in materials design of SiC-based composites.

2. Materials and methods

For wetting and infiltration tests, pure Si, as reference element, and three different Si-Me alloy compositions (Si-rich side) have been selected: Si-Me eutectics and two hypereutectic alloys. The alloys have been produced by mixing high pure Si and Me (3-4N GoodFellow©) and melted by arc-melting. Each as-produced alloy microstructure/composition have been checked by SEM/EDS analyses.

As wetting substrate, glassy-C (C_g-Alfa Aesar©), with a roughness \approx 20nm, has been chosen. A C-porous graphite preform (G_p: porosity \approx 90%; average porous radius \approx 3.0 μ , purity 99.7 %) has been selected as substrate for infiltration experiments.

All the aforementioned properties and characteristics have been carefully investigated as a function of operating conditions and composition. Contact heating sessile [2] and dispensed drop procedures [3] have been applied and experiments performed in the temperature range of (T_m+20)-1500°C. Interfacial phenomena and

resulting microstructures have been carefully analyzed in terms of thickness and composition of the reaction layer, by OM, SEM-EDS and 3D-Tomography techniques. Moreover, to detect the presence of ZrC as additional reaction product, Raman and XRD techniques have been used. In parallel, surface and bulk properties outcomes, i.e. surface tension and density data, have been compared with the predicted values obtained by applying Ideal solution, Quasi-Chemical Approximation for regular solution models as done in [4].

3. Results and discussion

In Figure 1, the evolution of wetting behavior of Si-27wt%Zr eutectics/C_g couple, within a contact heating experiment performed at T = 1350°C under an Ar (N60) static atmosphere, is shown. Spreading kinetics is also reported in terms of drop radius.

Fig. 1. Contact angle (θ) and drop base radius (R) as a function of time of Si-27%Zr/ C_g couple at T \approx 1350°C.

As can be seen, four different spreading stages have been observed. In particular, the stage (t₀-t₁) is typical of wetting experiments performed close to the melting point (T_m Si-27Zr \approx 1370°C [5]) by contact heating sessile drop method. After the melting (detected at T \approx 1350°C), the presence of SiO₂/ZrO₂-primary oxides at the surface delays the complete melting of the drop. Moreover, the oxide skin initially prevents the intimate contact between the melt phase and the substrate. In the second spreading stage (t₁-t₂), several changes in the dR/dt are evident: two possible reasons are 1) the progressive dissolution of the SiO₂ wetting barrier by liquid Si [1] and 2) the no homogeneous melting of the alloy drop. The general behaviour observed in this stage suggests that Si-27Zr/C_g wettability is governed

by the reaction at the triple line [1]. Within the third stage of spreading (t_2 - t_3) a linear dependency is again observed: reactivity is still the dominant mechanism. The drastic change of the slope suggests that “competitive” phenomena are evolving, strongly influencing the advancing contact angle. In Table 1, the equilibrium contact angle values measured at the end of wetting tests performed by contact heating sessile drop method on Si-Me eutectics/ C_g couples are reported.

Alloy [wt%]/ C_g	T [°C]	θ_f	Ref.
Si-37.5Co	1320	36	[2]
Si-37.5Co	1390	38	[2]
Si-37.5Co	1450	<15	[2]
Si-27Zr	1350	52	This work
Si-27Zr	1450	45	This work
Si-27Zr	1500	43	This work

Table 1. Final contact angle values (θ_f) as a function of temperature for Si-Me eutectic alloys (Me = Co, Zr)/ C_g

A strong T-dependency of contact angle value has been observed, as expected. Moreover, the higher values of contact angle measured for Si-Zr/ C_g system might be correlated to the higher surface tension value of Si-Zr liquid metal phase. As main outcome of the theoretical analysis on surface tension behavior as a function of Si-content reported in [4], the Si-Me eutectic alloys in the Si-rich phase, are well described by ideal/regular solution models. In addition, even if not detected by XRD and EDS analyses, the presence of ZrC, thermodynamically favoured as reaction product, might be the reason of a different resulting roughness/microstructure at the Si-Zr/ C_g interface. In Figure 2, the kinetics of infiltration of Si-37.5Co alloy/ G_p -preform as a function of temperature is shown.

Fig. 2. Evolution of R-Drop base radius during infiltration experiments performed on Si-37.5Co as a function of temperature under a vacuum of $P_{tot} = 10^{-2}$ Pa.

A strong T-dependency of the $R(t)$ and dR/dt has been observed, typically related to reactive mechanisms. In Figure 3, the evolution of Si-Me infiltrating eutectic melt phases (H-height of the drop as a function of time), i.e. Si-37.5Co and Si-27Zr, into porous graphite, observed at $T = 1450^\circ\text{C}$, is shown. With different infiltration kinetics, both Si-Me alloys spontaneously infiltrate porous graphite. Depending on the operative conditions, the alloying element (Me) might give competitive equilibria making kinetically favoured both SiC and Me-carbides (ZrC). In addition, the alloying element may actively influence the capillarity and fluid-dynamics during infiltration owing to its

own thermophysical properties (i.e. surface tension, viscosity, etc.).

Fig. 3. Kinetics of infiltration of Si-Me/ G_p at $T = 1450^\circ\text{C}$ and under a vacuum of $P_{tot} = 10^{-2}$ Pa.

4. Conclusions and works in progress

Wetting and infiltration experiments have been performed as a function of operating conditions (T, P_{tot} , etc.) and composition by contact heating.

The results obtained further confirm that reactivity at Si-Me/ C -preform interfaces is the main driven force controlling infiltration process. In particular, both wettability and infiltration processes are strongly dependent on temperature, Si-content and alloying element.

In order to analyze properly the wetting and infiltration kinetics under well-defined operating conditions, experiments will be performed also by dispensed drop method. This method will allow to produce fresh melt surfaces under oxides-free conditions. In addition, thermodynamic studies on Si-Me-C and Raman technique will be used to well distinguish among the produced carbides phases (i.e. SiC and Me-carbides).

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